

MCAA
MARIE CURIE ALUMNI ASSOCIATION

Transformative ERA Act for researchers

Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA)

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About the Marie Curie Alumni Association

The Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) is a global network with more than 24,000 members from over 150 countries, open to past and present beneficiaries of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) programme, including researchers, their supervisors and MSCA project managers. The MCAA aims to connect the MSCA community, supporting career development initiatives for MCAA members and advocating for research and researchers.

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Executive Summary

The Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) thanks the European Commission for the opportunity to contribute to the public consultation on the forthcoming European Research Area (ERA) Act. Representing a global network of more than 24,000 researchers across all career stages and research fields, spanning over 150 countries, the MCAA provides its input through the consultation survey, reflecting the perspectives and lived experiences of mobile researchers working across Europe and beyond. Our recommendations are the following:

1. Strengthen investment in research and development (R&D) and increase it to reach the 3% gross domestic product (GDP) target

- Establish binding national public R&D investment targets to reach 3% of GDP, with at least 1–1.25% GDP dedicated to public R&D investment.
- Keep public research and innovation (R&I) funding as the backbone. Private investment should complement, not replace public funding, especially for frontier and fundamental research. Require transparency on private-sector participation and contributions in publicly funded research.
- Protect civil R&I budgets from dilution or reclassification under broader competitiveness/security instruments. Consider fiscal flexibilities for R&I, analogous to defence, to enable sustained reforms.

2. Greater alignment of R&I investments, policies and programmes across the European Union (EU)

- Reduce fragmentation via governance coherence, interoperability and complementarity, not by steering research topics in bottom-up programmes.
- Safeguard the autonomy and non-directional character of excellence-driven instruments such as the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) and European Research Council (ERC).
- Simplify European Partnerships: improve transparency, reduce administrative burden, and enhance accessibility, especially for Widening countries, smaller institutions and individual researchers.

3. Improve the general conditions for research and researchers in Europe

- Embed a researcher-centred approach with enforceable minimum standards that reduce precarity and support mobility and training, building on the principles of the European Charter for Researchers as a common reference framework across the ERA
- Freedom of scientific research: Introduce EU-level, legally binding safeguards, address precarity as a risk factor, enable proportionate conditionality in EU funding, and establish an independent European ombudsperson.
- Gender equality and equal opportunities: Strengthen accountability through minimum Gender Equality Plan (GEP) requirements and improve support for caregivers, including by promoting flexible, career-stage-sensitive eligibility criteria in funding and mobility schemes to accommodate non-linear career paths.

- **Careers & mobility:** Ensure employment contracts with full social security (including for doctoral candidates), develop a European researcher contract template, mandate R1–R4 use in vacancies, accelerate recognition of qualifications, and simplify visa procedures.
- **Knowledge circulation:** Reinforce immediate open access, rights retention, and the making findings Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR), invest in open infrastructures, and transform research assessment.
- **Knowledge valorisation:** Broaden recognition in careers, strengthen intersectoral mobility, and support institutional capacity without overly prescriptive Intellectual Property (IP) models.

4. Aligning guidance on AI in research

- Reduce fragmentation through harmonised, research-sensitive EU guidance and capacity-building and rely on existing integrity/whistleblowing mechanisms rather than duplicative AI-specific systems.

5. International cooperation and research security

- Establish common, risk-based principles and coordination to strengthen trust and resilience while preserving openness and academic freedom based on like-minded values.

Europe's competitiveness and resilience depend on investing in people and protecting excellence-driven, bottom-up instruments. The MCAA calls for a substantially strengthened, ring-fenced and autonomous MSCA, delivered via a dedicated MSCA Work Programme preserving its fully bottom-up, curiosity-driven and open nature, with at least €25 billion reserved for it within the overall budget of €220 billion of the 10th EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (FP10).

Transformative ERA Act for researchers

The Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) thanks the European Commission for the opportunity to contribute to the public consultation on the forthcoming European Research Area (ERA) Act. Representing a global network of more than 24,000 researchers across all career stages and research fields, spanning over 150 countries, the MCAA provides its input through the consultation survey, reflecting the perspectives and lived experiences of mobile researchers working across Europe and beyond.

This submission follows up on the [MCAA's earlier contribution](#) to the Commission's call for evidence and now provides the Association's consolidated positions in response to the public consultation questionnaire. It is grounded in evidence and recommendations set out in the MCAA's recent policy work, that reflect both the lived experiences of mobile researchers and the demonstrated structural impact of excellence-driven instruments such as the MSCA.

Across all survey responses, one overarching message is clear: Europe's research competitiveness, resilience and strategic autonomy depend on sustained public investment in people and knowledge, supported by strong framework conditions and protected excellence-driven instruments. In this context, the MCAA reiterates its call for substantially enhanced support for the MSCA, including a ring-fenced budget of at least €25 billion under the 10th EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (FP10) within an overall €220 billion Framework Programme, delivered through a dedicated MSCA Work Programme and preserving its fully bottom-up, curiosity-driven and open nature, as well as its institutional autonomy.

Below are the MCAA's recommendations for each part of the survey, excluding sub-chapter 3.2.3 "European Research Infrastructure Consortia".

1 Strengthen R&D investment and bring it up to the 3% GDP target to address the current lack of investment

Chronic underinvestment in research and development (R&D), particularly uneven public spending across Member States, remains a key driver of Europe's innovation gap. Reaching the target of 3% of the gross domestic product (GDP), with at least 1–1.25% GDP dedicated to public R&D investment, is essential not only for competitiveness but also for societal resilience, strategic autonomy, and talent attraction.

EU-level legislation should establish binding national public R&D investment targets, supported by multiannual roadmaps, monitoring and accountability mechanisms. Public investment must remain the backbone of the system, while private investment should complement, not substitute, robust public funding, especially for frontier and fundamental research. Transparency on private-sector participation in publicly funded research is therefore essential. Civil R&D budgets should be protected from dilution or reclassification under broader competitiveness or security instruments.

The MSCA illustrates why investment in people delivers systemic returns: since 1996 it has supported nearly 150,000 researchers, who are changing the support to economic, societal and technological impact. Demand significantly outstrips capacity, as reflected in the 17,058 proposals submitted to the MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships 2025 call, highlighting the urgent need to scale the programme while preserving its excellence-driven, bottom-up design¹.

¹ Marie Curie Alumni Association (2025). [Impact of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions \(MSCA\). Driving knowledge, innovation and EU competitiveness.](#)

2 Greater alignment of R&I investments, policies, and programmes between the EU and Member States, and between Member States

Greater alignment of R&I investments is needed to reduce fragmentation and improve efficiency, but this must not translate into increased directionality or concentration of funding around narrowly defined priorities. Europe's strength lies in a balanced ecosystem that combines system-level coordination with independent, bottom-up funding instruments.

The ERA Act should therefore operate within framework conditions, ensuring governance coherence, interoperability, and complementarity – not by steering the research topics of bottom-up programmes. The MSCA experience further demonstrates why preserving bottom-up approach and freedom is crucial in fast-moving fields: The programme has supported over 500 projects focusing on artificial intelligence (AI) across Horizon 2020 and already more than 500 new AI projects in the first half of Horizon Europe, supporting over 2,000 researchers². This demonstrates that curiosity-driven funding anticipates and builds capacity in emerging areas ahead of formal policy prioritisation. The autonomy and non-directional nature of excellence-based instruments such as the MSCA and European Research Council (ERC) should be explicitly safeguarded, as these programmes are proven engines of talent attraction, skills development, interdisciplinary collaboration, and global competitiveness precisely because they allow researchers to define their own paths.

Simplifying the European Partnerships landscape, improving transparency, and reducing administrative complexity would enhance participation, particularly for individual researchers, smaller institutions and organisations in the Widening countries.

² Marie Curie Alumni Association (2025). *Impact of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA). Driving knowledge, innovation and EU competitiveness.*

3 Improve the general conditions for research and researchers in Europe

Improving general conditions is not ancillary; it is the enabling environment for excellence, mobility, innovation, and trust in science. The ERA Act should anchor a researcher-centred approach, including enforceable minimum standards that reduce precarity, support mobility, and strengthen institutional accountability, building on the principles of the European Charter for Researchers as a common reference framework across the ERA.

3.1 Upholding the fundamental values of the European Research Area

3.1.1 Freedom of scientific research

Freedom of scientific research is foundational to the ERA and a prerequisite for excellence, innovation, and democratic resilience, yet protections remain uneven and insufficiently enforceable. Researchers increasingly face political, economic, and societal pressures, including interference in research agendas, public harassment, and reputational attacks, that can lead to self-censorship and undermine trust in science.

Precarious employment conditions further weaken scientific freedom by limiting researchers' independence and making them vulnerable to external influence. Therefore, protecting the freedom of research requires addressing structural conditions of research careers alongside legal safeguards.

The ERA Act should establish uniform, legally binding protection of the freedom of scientific research at the EU level, complemented by minimum national standards and clear core rights for researchers, as well as rights and obligations for research-performing organisations. Compliance mechanisms are needed; linking access to EU funding to respect for academic freedom can be appropriate if applied proportionately, transparently, and with due process. Establishing an independent European ombudsperson for academic freedom would provide a trusted mechanism to support researchers facing undue interference and to monitor systemic risks across the ERA. This mechanism could be complemented by systematic feedback collection during and after publicly funded research projects, ensuring early detection of risks and reducing the burden on individual researchers to report challenges. Legal measures should be complemented by awareness-raising, training, and institutional support to strengthen a culture of scientific freedom, integrity, and responsibility.

3.1.2 Gender equality and equal opportunities

Gender equality and equal opportunities are fundamental ERA values and essential to research excellence and societal relevance. Progress has been made at the EU level, particularly through Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) as an eligibility criterion for EU funding, yet uptake and implementation remain uneven across Member States and sectors. Establishing legally binding minimum requirements for GEPs at the EU level, while allowing flexibility in implementation, would strengthen accountability and ensure that plans deliver meaningful change rather than formal compliance.

Evidence shows that well-designed programmes can deliver tangible progress: the MSCA provides a strong example of gender-responsive design, with around 42% of MSCA fellows being women³, reflecting balanced participation across disciplines and career stages. However, structural barriers persist in funding and mobility schemes, notably rigid eligibility criteria based on maximum years after a PhD, which disproportionately disadvantage researchers with caregiving responsibilities, even where formal extensions (e.g., for maternity or parental leave) exist. Further progress requires sustained attention to integrating gender and other social factors into R&I content, improved support for researchers with caregiving responsibilities, and more flexible, career-stage-sensitive eligibility approaches that better reflect non-linear research trajectories.

3.2 Ensuring the free circulation of researchers and scientific knowledge

3.2.1 Researchers' careers and mobility

Attractive and sustainable research careers are a prerequisite for the free circulation of knowledge and talent, yet legal, administrative, and structural barriers continue to undermine mobility and long-term prospects, particularly for early-career researchers and researchers from third countries.

Evidence collected by the MCAA indicates that fixed-term contracts, inadequate social security coverage, a lack of contractual transparency, and complex administrative procedures all contribute to reducing the attractiveness of research careers. Visa and residence permit requirements remain a significant barrier, disproportionately affecting third-country nationals researchers, which limits both recruitment of third-country nationals and intra-EU mobility, despite Directive (EU) 2016/801 on the conditions of entry and residence of third-country nationals for purposes including research.

As highlighted in the statement⁴, the ERA Act should strengthen legal certainty and minimum standards for research employment by ensuring that researchers at all career stages are employed with full access to social security. Developing a European researcher contract

³ Marie Curie Alumni Association (2025). *Impact of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA). Driving knowledge, innovation and EU competitiveness.*

template, combined with minimum contractual standards and multilingual transparency, would improve onboarding, reduce precarity, and facilitate mobility. Career transparency should also be enhanced through a binding requirement to map national and institutional career structures to the R1–R4 research profiles and to use them in all research vacancies, improving recognition of experience, employability, and cross-sector mobility. Accelerated recognition of academic qualifications, simplified visa procedures (up to a certain period beyond the end of contract), and reduced administrative burdens are necessary to ensure that mobility does not come at the expense of social security, family life, or career stability.

3.2.2 Free circulation of scientific knowledge

Significant progress has been made on open access and Open Science across the ERA through EU funding requirements, institutional policies, and shared infrastructures. However, structural barriers persist, notably rising costs of accessing and publishing research outputs, and limited transparency around agreements between public institutions and publishers, posing risks to equitable access and the sustainability of Open Science.

EU-level legislation can further improve its approach by consolidating and reinforcing existing initiatives good practices: ensuring immediate open access to publicly funded outputs, supporting rights retention, mandating data management plans, and ensuring publicly funded research data and outputs are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) and accessible through open, trusted infrastructures. Continued investment in open, interoperable infrastructures, including support for the Diamond Publishing Model (e.g. Open Research Europe), remains essential.

Crucially, research assessment systems play a central enabling role in the free circulation of knowledge and in achieving wider ERA objectives. Persistently misaligned assessment practices—still prioritising publication counts and journal prestige over research quality, openness, integrity, diverse contributions and mobility across sectors—remain a major barrier not only to Open Science, but also to progress in areas such as diversity and inclusion, research integrity and intersectoral mobility. Aligning researcher assessment with Open Science principles is therefore indispensable for an open, efficient, and competitive ERA.

3.2.3 Knowledge valorisation

Knowledge valorisation is an essential pathway through which publicly funded research delivers societal, economic, and policy value. Yet structural barriers continue to limit effective uptake across the ERA. A central obstacle remains the misalignment of research assessment systems that continue to prioritise publications and citations and provide limited recognition for socio-economic impact activities, such as collaboration with industry and public authorities, standardisation, and public and policy engagement.

Employment conditions also constrain valorisation: limited flexibility for two-way mobility between academia and other sectors restricts co-creation and exchange. Expanding intersectoral mobility schemes with guaranteed rights to return would enhance valorisation without undermining careers.

EU-level action can add value by incentivising institutions to reward broader contributions in career progression and by supporting mobility between sectors, while keeping Intellectual Property (IP) and professionalisation approaches adaptable and avoiding overly prescriptive models. A balanced approach to valorisation beyond commercialisation alone will strengthen the societal relevance and impact of European research.

3.3 Aligning guidance on AI in research.

AI is increasingly embedded across disciplines. Its responsible use requires clarity, consistency, transparency, and trust. Fragmented ethical and governance frameworks create legal uncertainty and administrative burden, particularly in cross-border and interdisciplinary collaborations. The ERA Act should strengthen coherence through harmonised guidance and capacity-building rather than prescriptive regulation of research practice. Embedding EU-wide, research-sensitive principles and harmonised guidance on ethical and responsible AI in research would provide a common reference point while allowing flexibility across disciplines. Strengthening institutional capacity to implement and monitor AI governance is equally important. Regarding potential misuse, many organisations already have whistleblowing, research integrity, and ethics reporting mechanisms. Prioritising awareness and usability of these existing, trusted channels is more proportionate than creating parallel AI-specific systems.

3.4 Improving consistency in approaches to international cooperation and research security across the EU

Academic freedom, international cooperation, and openness are fundamental to the ERA, but they must be accompanied by proportionate, coherent strategies to research security. Differences across Member States and institutional autonomy undermine a joint European stance and raise uncertainties for researchers engaged in international collaboration.

EU-level legislation can add clear value by recognising research security as a shared concern and setting minimum requirements for a consistent, risk-based approach across Member States, focused on principles, coordination, and capacity-building, while preserving flexibility for different contexts and respecting academic freedom. A coherent EU framework aligned with existing recommendations by the European Council would strengthen resilience and mutual trust while maintaining Europe's openness and attractiveness as a global research leader.

Final remarks

The MCAA welcomes the European Commission's ambition to make the ERA Act a transformative instrument that moves from aspiration to implementation. This requires serious investment, enforceable protections for fundamental values, and structural measures that improve careers and mobility. It also requires explicit safeguarding of Europe's excellence-driven, bottom-up engines, most notably a substantially strengthened, ring-fenced and autonomous MSCA, with at least €25 billion dedicated to it under the overall €220 billion budget within FP10. The MCAA stands ready to continue contributing evidence from its community of over 24,000 MSCA beneficiaries to help shape an ERA that is open, competitive, fair, and globally attractive.

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